

Organizational climate and quality of work-life in the creativity of teachers

Masduki Ahmad, Suryadi Suryadi, Matin Matin, Sugiarto Sugiarto

Department of Education Management, Faculty of Science Education, Universitas Negeri Jakarta, Jakarta, Indonesia

Article Info

Article history:

Received Aug 18, 2021

Revised Nov 29, 2022

Accepted Jan 2, 2023

Keywords:

Creativity

Organizational climate

Quality of work life

ABSTRACT

This study analyzed the effect of organizational climate and quality of work-life on teachers' creativity throughout state vocational high schools in Serang, Indonesia during the COVID-19 pandemic. This work involved 164 civil servant teachers in state vocational high schools in Serang, Indonesia as the sample. As the major analysis tool, we used a multiple linear regression model. The hypothesis test used the t-test and f-test. The study revealed that: i) Organizational climate positively and significantly influenced the civil servant teachers' creativity amid the COVID-19 pandemic with a significance value of .000 ($\alpha < .005$); ii) The quality of work-life also had a positive and significant effect on the teachers' creativity during this difficult situation has significance value of .000 ($\alpha < .005$); and iii) The quality of their work influenced both organizational climate and the creativity of state vocational high school teachers living in Serang, Indonesia, with a determination coefficient of .861 or 86.1% during the pandemic.

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Corresponding Author:

Masduki Ahmad

Department of Education Management, Faculty of Science Education, Universitas Negeri Jakarta

Rawamangun, Pulo Gadung, East Jakarta 13220, Jakarta, Indonesia

Email: masduki@unj.ac.id

1. INTRODUCTION

Acquiring education is of paramount significance for human beings, whether they undergo formal or non-formal education. Education intends to bring them the chance to be useful to other individuals and the environment. Formal education usually takes place in schools, with teachers as one of the crucial elements and the main booster because they play a role in delivering insightful information to the students. Teachers are directly involved in influencing the quality of education in schools.

As teachers must fulfill professional competence as quality educators, they need to be highly creative. Creativity is defined as innovative ideas that can turn into an opportunity [1]. Accordingly, creativity refers to new ideas that will become a good opportunity if such ideas are put to use well. In this context, being creative will lead the teachers to generate a great chance in the learning process. Creativity is an educational approach associated with the general concept of teaching creativity [2]. Besides, creativity relates to improving the teaching style to become a new one. Being creative is necessary since numerous jobs today are transformed rapidly with the advancement of information technology in this digital-driven era of globalization [3]. Teachers' creativity is important for themselves and the organization (school) where they work [4]. A teaching and learning process requires many dimensions of creativity in its interactions [5]. In addition, Narayanan argued that creativity is the art of producing new ideas, approaches, or acts. Students unable to be creative and innovative, the teaching process should also be such [6]. This notion implies that the students' creativity is also affected by the teachers' creativity.

Creativity is the production of new ideas or suitable works [7], meaning that creative teachers manage to bring up new concepts in their work environment. Similarly, McShane and Glinow pointed out that creativity refers to the process of evolving original and contributing ideas that are socially acknowledged [8]. Thus, people with high creativity can expand their existing ideas to contribute to their practice fields. The fact is that creativity is not genetic but is obtained from habits, which means that creativity is an ability that can be trained [9]. Creativity will come up when a person has motivation, imagination, and curiosity [10].

For this reason, it will be much easier for teachers with strong motivation to be creative. Creativity is one's ability to raise new ideas and expand them to reach precise and optimal results of what has been done. In this case, teachers will achieve the best results in the learning process if they are highly creative. Such creativity can help them lead the students to also arrive at more ideal results because their creativity in teaching makes the process more varied with new ideas. On top of that, creativity will emerge when an individual is in a good state, influenced by several factors: the organizational climate where s/he works.

The organizational climate in question describes members' perceptions of their work environment [11]. While Harizlinardi, Arisandy, and Happyana [12] explained that organizational climate is an organization's internal environment or psychology. The organizational climate must be conducive so that members' perceptions of the atmosphere in the organization also become better. Organizational climate is also described as a description of the condition of organizational culture [13]. A good organizational climate will create conditions that support its members to work more optimally. This is in line with previous study [14], which stated that organizational climate is a quality of the internal environment that is felt relatively by each member based on experience and influences, his/her behavior can also be said to be the characteristic value of the organization. It explained that organizational climate is not only a picture of the atmosphere in an organization, but the organizational climate affects how its members will act.

According to previous study, organizational climate is a set of attributes that can be felt in a particular organization, department, or unit [15]. The climate felt by members of an organization is almost certainly the same. Olsson *et al.* [16] stated that organizational climate refers to patterns of behavior, attitudes, and feelings that characterize life in organizations. In addition, Diputra, Agung, and Kepramareni stated that organizational climate is a collection of environmental patterns that determine motivation to emerge so that it directly affects organizational performance [17]. Organizational climate is one of the factors that can lead to motivation in members of an organization, thus affecting the organization's overall performance. Organizational climate is how employees view their organization and its goals [18]. From some of these descriptions, it can be concluded that organizational climate is the atmosphere of the work environment that can be felt by members of the organization and can influence these members for their actions while in the organization. In a few words, organizational climate refers to organizational members' work environment and can influence their acts in the organization. Alongside organizational climate, quality of work-life (QWL) as well contributes to teachers' creativity.

According to Gibson, Ivancevich, and Konopaske, quality of work-life is a management concept that strives to enhance employee perspectives, modify routines, and provide workers opportunities to improve their quality [1]. It was a condition in which members of an organization prioritize their welfare and quality of work-life or concern for one's experience in the work environment. In addition, the quality of work-life is related to the welfare of employees in an organizational work environment [19].

The concept of quality of work life relates to whether or not a person enjoys their workplace [20]. So, the quality of life is a person's view of the work environment. An employee's views about many aspects of their work, ranging from the work environment to the stability of the employment itself, are reflected in the quality of their work-life [21]. That is different from job satisfaction because that involves almost all aspects of one's world of work. QWL boosts productivity and makes better use of human resources in an organization [22]. This indicates that one of the attempts to increase the leverage of members of the organization in creating work output is to improve the quality of work-life. Akar [23] also explained that when a company strives to safeguard its workers' well-being and redesigns work to meet this objective, employees are more likely to become more helpful, productive, and happy individuals.

The QWL in schools is a main source of concern. Schools need to make their teachers feel satisfied in carrying out their work; where this can be achieved by paying attention to the quality of working life at the school, which consists of providing opportunities for teachers to make decisions regarding their work, workplace design, and their need to be more creative [24]. The quality of working life in schools is important because teachers feel it is an important factor in determining the quality of education. The quality of education requires designing a working system that can improve teachers' work-life experience, increasing their commitment and motivation to achieve their goals. For a teacher, the quality of work-life is crucial [25].

In an organization, work-life balance is important. As organizations where teachers teach, schools are responsible for considering work-life balance. Organizations require a high-quality working environment to achieve their objectives [26]. It indicates that the success of organizational goals is also dependent on the

organization's overall work-life quality. This is similar to Swamy and Nanjundeswaraswamy [27], who stated that an advanced quality of work-life also helps meet staff demands while still achieving company objectives effectively and efficiently. So, good quality of work-life not just helps the organization achieve its goals effectively and efficiently but also helps employees meet their needs. It will certainly improve the performance of employees in the organization.

When an organization produces a QWL approach, it is believed that its employees' performance will improve. There were three factors affect a person's performance: the quality of work-life, organizational commitment, and job satisfaction [28]. Employee commitment and job satisfaction are two of the company's objectives in implementing quality rules [29]. Quality of work-life puts forward the expectations of members of the organization to be fulfilled. The extent to which an individual interacts with and perceives life is directly connected to the conditions of their work environment is referred to as quality of work-life [30]. From several previous opinions, the quality of work-life can be summarized as an approach is taken to improve the quality of the work environment, so that members of an organization/employee can be more prosperous and carried out consciously and continuously.

Creativity has become a challenge for Indonesian teachers amid the COVID-19 pandemic. During this hard time, the government decides to implement distance learning for elementary school to university students. This undoubtedly changes the students' learning culture who get used to face-to-face learning. Such changes will eventually boomerang on the government if teachers do not maximize their roles in taking advantage of today's situation to teach. As a result, teachers must go outside the box to provide remote learning opportunities.

Teachers are demanded to have a superb ability to turn classroom learning into online learning, not to mention that such a learning model has not been previously implemented [31]. Online learning will be problematic when teachers do not manage to improve their creativity during the teaching process. For instance, when the teacher constantly assigns the students to make a video, they will find it monotonous. Due to the unvaried learning methods, students encounter the same situation every day, causing them to play around or use their phones without paying attention to the lesson. That is what happens nowadays when most students use gadgets for others than studying, implying that the learning objectives are not reached optimally. Moreover, distance learning will make it harder for teachers to directly monitor students' learning outcomes.

The lack of teachers' creativity leads to a serious problem, let alone that the government has no idea when distance learning will get back to the classroom. Red-zone regions are also unlikely to perform face-to-face learning shortly, so that social distancing remains applicable and the spread of the virus can be suppressed. Java Island, Indonesia, currently has the most positive cases of COVID-19. On September 30th, 2020 (when this research was conducted), Jakarta is the region with the highest number of cases (72,736 cases or 25.7% out of the total cases in Indonesia) [32], followed by East Java, Central Java, West Java, Banten, and Yogyakarta.

Banten even extended the restrictions for a month due to the increasing number of confirmed cases in this province. As a result, the teaching and learning process is carried out through an online system. As of March 9th, 2022, Serang City, Banten, is the only city with Community Activities Restrictions Enforcement (PPKM) level 3, which means face-to-face learning in schools only takes place with a capacity of 50%. In addition, as of March 9th, 2022, Banten ranks 5th as the province with the largest contributor to COVID-19 cases in Indonesia, amounting to 189,330 cases or 9.7% of the total cases in Indonesia.

On that ground, analyzing teachers' creativity as the main problem is interesting to the author. Indeed, several studies have currently examined the same variables. Abdullah *et al.* [33] focus on examining the impact of organizational climate on creativity and Elnagar *et al.* [34] focus on the effect of QWL on creativity. However, it is a novelty that no one has studied organizational climate, QWL, and creativity simultaneously. It will be a significant benefit to this research. This research also explores the effect of organizational climate and work-life quality on civil servant teachers' creativity throughout state vocational high schools in Serang amid the COVID-19 pandemic. This present work is expected to raise the awareness of school members, including teachers, about increasing the distance learning quality during this time.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

This study relied on a quantitative approach. Therefore, the results of this study will be in the form of numbers and data, which the researcher will ultimately interpret. Meanwhile, the research model used is a multiple linear regression model. The questionnaire is a sheet containing several questions with a standard structure [35]. The questionnaire, encompassing close-ended questions with provided answers, was composed using Google Form.

Additionally, the questionnaire utilized the Likert scale in measuring the variables of organizational climate (X1), quality of work-life (X2), and creativity (Y). Before the research instruments are distributed, the instruments are tested first. The test of this instrument is done by testing the validity and reliability of the

instrument. Validity shows the degree of accuracy between data on the object and data collected by researchers. At the same time, reliability is concerned with the degree of consistency or accuracy of data within a certain time interval [36].

The population in this study were Civil Servant Teachers of State Vocational High Schools in Serang City, Indonesia amounting to 279 people. This study employed a basic random sampling approach in which all teachers were given a chance to be part of the research sample. The sample is part of the population which also represents the entire population. According to Arikunto, the sample is typical of the examined demographic [37]. From that population, the research sample was 164 teachers. This figure was calculated using the Slovin formula with a 5% error rate (0.05).

Since the study employed the multiple linear regression model, several analysis requirement tests were conducted. The normality test aims to determine whether the data from the three research variables obtained from data are normally distributed—the linearity test determines whether there is a linear relationship between variables. The multicollinearity test aims to know the regression model in a study that found a correlation between the independent variables (X). The heteroscedasticity test determines if there is an inequality of variance between the residuals of one observation and those of another in a regression model [38]. The purpose of the multiple linear regression model was to find the effect of variables X1 and X2 on Y. The hypothesis test was also conducted using the t-test and the f-test to determine the variables' partial and simultaneous impact. Multiple linear regression models are used to calculate the coefficient of determination which shows the percentage of influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. Statistical calculations were carried out using SPSS 25.

The hypotheses of this research were: i) Organizational climate positively and significantly influenced the civil servant teachers' creativity in state vocational high school in Serang; ii) The quality of work-life had a positive and significant effect on the creativity of civil servant teachers in state vocational high school in Serang; iii) Both organizational climate and quality of work-life affected the creativity of civil servant teachers in state vocational high school in Serang.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Results

3.1.1. Analysis prerequisite test

The results of the analysis prerequisite test are as listed in Table 1. The normality test, calculated using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov formula and SPSS 25, yielded an Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) value of .200. Since the value of Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) is $.200 > .05$, the study findings are often disseminated. A linearity test shows that the independent and dependent variables have a linear relationship—this research comprised organizational climate and QWL variables, and creativity variables. The significant value of variable X1 (organizational environment) towards variable Y (creativity) in the preceding table is $.322 > .05$, indicating that the two variables are linearly related. From the table, the significant value of variable X2 (QWL) towards variable Y (creativity) is $.091 > .05$, suggesting that the two variables have a linear relationship.

Table 1. Analysis prerequisite test

Test name	Result	Requirement
Normality test	0.200	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) $> .05$
Linearity test	0.322 (X1 towards Y) 0.091 (X2 towards Y)	Sig. $> .05$
Multicollinearity test	0.178 (tolerance value) 5.627 (value of VIF)	Tolerance value > 0.10 VIF < 10.00
Heteroscedasticity test	0.551	Sig. (2-tailed)

A multicollinearity test aims to determine the correlation between independent variables. A good regression model does not indicate multicollinearity with a tolerance value $> .10$ and a VIF value < 10.00 . It is shown that the tolerance value gets $.178 > .10$; thereby, no indication of multicollinearity takes place. The decision can also be made by considering the value of VIF. Since the value of VIF is $5.627 < 10.00$, there is no indication of multicollinearity in the present study.

A heteroscedasticity test determines whether or not a regression model has a constant residual variance from one observation to another. In this study, the heteroscedasticity test was the Rank Spearman test, in which the choice is made based on the significance value $> .05$, which eliminates heteroscedasticity concerns. From Table 1, it is shown that the Sig. (2-tailed) value for the organizational climate variable is $.551 > .05$. Meanwhile, the value of Sig. (2-tailed) for quality of work-life variable is $.943 > .05$. Because both significance values are more than $.05$, there is no concern with heteroscedasticity in this regression model.

3.1.2. Multiple linear regression analysis

Table 2 shows that the results obtained for the multiple linear regression model for this study which was obtained using the SPSS 25 version. The coefficient of determination from (1) is listed in Table 3. The regression equation described previously yields the coefficient of determination. A coefficient is a number that indicates how many independent variables (X) impact the dependent variable simultaneously (Y). Following the result, it is found that the determination coefficient is .861 or 86.1%. Consequently, variables X1 (organizational climate) and X2 (quality of work-life) simultaneously contribute 86.1% to variable Y (creativity). The remaining 13.9% is affected by another variable not examined in this research.

Table 2. Multiple linear regression analysis

Variables	Regression coefficients
Constant	-6.973
Organizational climate (X1)	.626
Quality of work-life (X2)	.391

From Table 2, the regression is in (1):

$$Y = -6.973 + .626 + .391 \quad (1)$$

Table 3. Value of the determination coefficient

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the estimate
.928	.861	.859	4.937

3.1.3. T-test

After using SPSS 25, here are the results of the t-test for this study which are listed in Table 4. As indicated by the significant value of each independent variable, organizational environment (X1) and quality of work-life (X2) both impact teachers' creativity (Y). The organizational climate has a significance value of .000, which is less than .05. Furthermore, this variable's t-count is 8.139, which is greater than the 1.974 in the t (161) table. Thus, the organizational climate affects teachers' creativity. Likewise, QWL (X2) achieves a significance value of .000, which is also less than .05. The value of the t-count of this variable is 5.489, which is greater than the t (161) table of 1.974, signifying that teachers' creativity is affected by QWL.

Table 4. T-test result

Variables	tcount	Sig.
Organizational climate (X1)	8.139	.000
Quality of work-life (X2)	5.489	.000

3.1.4. F-test

After using SPSS 25, the results of the F-test for this study are listed in Table 5. The table shows that organizational climate and quality of work-life simultaneously contribute to creativity, in which the significance value of (Sig.) is .000, which is less than .05. The conclusion may also be formed by looking at the value of F-count, which is $499.137 > F(2,162)$ in the 3.05. In short, organizational climate and QWL have a simultaneous influence on teachers' creativity.

Table 5. F-test result

Model	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Regression	24,335.147	2	12,167.573	499.137	.000
Residual	3,924.731	161	24.377		
Total	28,259.878	163			

3.2. Discussion

This study investigates the effect of organizational climate and work-life quality on civil servant teachers' creativity in the site area during the COVID-19 pandemic. The invention has revealed that organizational climate and quality of work-life do simultaneously influence the teachers' creativity, as shown by the significance value of $F\text{-test} = .000 < .05$. Next, the value of the F-count is $499.137 > F\text{-table of } 3.05$. The effect of both variables on teachers' creativity is measured at 86.1%, as seen in the value of $R^2 = .861$.

Consequently, organizational climate and quality of work-life simultaneously influence the civil servant teachers' creativity in state vocational high schools in Serang. In other words, the third hypothesis is accepted. It is also found that organizational climate affects teachers' creativity, as shown by the significance value of $.000 < .05$ and the value of $t\text{-count} = 8.139 > t(161)$ table of 1.974. Hence, organizational climate positively and significantly influences the teachers' creativity in the site area; the more improved the organizational climate, the higher teachers' creativity.

These findings support Terry *et al.* [39] which found that organizational climate is one of the elements that influence teacher creativity in schools. The influence given by the organizational climate on creativity is positive. When the organizational climate increases, teachers' creativity will also increase. A well-maintained organizational climate will add a positive impression on teachers at work. It will make the teacher more enthusiastic in carrying out their work. It certainly positively affects teachers' creativity because teachers with strong interests and high morale will also produce high creativity [40].

Organizational climate is one of the important factors that affect one's creativity [41]. This study found that the organizational climate is one of the important factors that can increase employees' creativity in Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises. The organizational climate does have a positive effect on a person's creativity, where a conducive organizational climate will be able to increase the creativity of the people who are in it. That also applies to teachers with schools as the organizations they follow. A conducive organizational climate referred to here is a conducive school environment. When the school environment support in teachers' creativity, the teacher will be more open to doing something more creative for the betterment of the school.

There is a significant relationship between the dimensions and indicators of organizational climate and employee creativity. These dimensions and indicators include cooperation and pretending to work [42]. These results indicate that organizational climate is related to one's creativity in the organization. In this case, the school is the organization where the teacher works. If the organization supports teachers in developing creativity, then the organization is good [43].

Meanwhile, other study demonstrated that the organizational climate has a substantial impact on the creative behaviors of employees at Jordanian pharmaceutical companies [44]. The study also showed that organizational climate dimensions such as flexibility, responsibility, group commitment, reward, and clarity affect the creativity of members of an organization. A positive organizational climate can create a comfortable work environment for employees to innovate and find new ways to complete tasks. This is the same thing that applies to teachers, where a good school organizational climate will influence teachers to be more creative in providing learning. Teachers should have new ideas to provide learning, especially during the current online learning period. That is because the good or bad implementation of the curriculum is very dependent on the activities and creativity of the teacher in describing and realizing the curriculum [45].

The current study also reveals that QWL influences teachers' creativity, as shown by the significance value of $.000 < .05$ and the $t\text{-count} = 5.489 > t(161)$ table of 1.974. As a result, the quality of construction has a positive and substantial impact on teacher creativity in schools; the higher the quality of employees, the higher the creativity of teachers. The findings of this study are also consistent with the findings of previous study. The study revealed that the quality of professionals might boost employees' creative behavior in Egypt [35]. The quality of their work-life influences a person's creativity. School as a work environment where teachers teach greatly affects the teacher's creativity. Teachers' creative behavior will increase if they have a good quality of life at work. That is significant because a teacher with a high level of creativity would improve the quality of learning.

The results of this study are also supported by Priscilla, Gyambrah, and Boakye that examined the effect of creativity on employees' work-life quality in several Ghanaian organizations. In this study, it was found that employee creativity significantly influences QWL, which means that if the creative climate is felt, the QWL can also be felt [46]. Schools with advanced QWL will develop a creative culture for their teachers. Of course, getting used to this creative culture is very important now that teachers must always think about new ideas that can be applied to online learning. That is where the role of the principal as top management is needed. Forming a good QWL will make teachers creative in developing online learning.

QWL has a significant and positive effect on innovative performance [47]. Creativity has a substantial and good impact on QWL. It proves that the QWL does positively influence the creativity of an individual in an organization. Innovation and creativity are two things that are always interrelated, where creativity is a process of forming ideas. Innovation leads to the next step in the implication of ideas through practice or products [48]. Employees' creativity in the information technology industry in India is partly influenced by the quality of their work-life [49]. This study also shows that several factors influence employee creativity, including workload and stress. QWL in an organization is affected by workload and stress, and it will still cause a decrease in employee creativity. This factor is, of course, also considered because these two factors can be another reason why employee creativity in an organization decreases.

The research by Mahmoodi *et al.* showed a positive and significant relationship between QWL and teacher creativity, which means that if QWL is in good condition, the teacher will need more creative [50]. This research also highlights the aspects of quality work-life that have a beneficial impact on creativity, including participation in decision-making, training and education opportunities, democracy in schools, facilities, welfare, and work design in schools and workspaces. Thus, paying attention to these factors in the quality of school working life will produce more creative teachers at work.

4. CONCLUSION

This study analyzed the effect of organizational climate and work-life quality on civil servant teachers' creativity throughout state vocational high schools in Serang amid the COVID-19 pandemic. This study formulates several conclusions: i) Organizational climate positively and significantly influences the teachers' creativity; ii) Quality of work-life positively and significantly affects the teachers' creativity; and iii) Organizational climate and quality of work-life have an impact on civil servant teachers' creativity in the site area during the COVID-19 pandemic with 86.1%.

The implications can be applied in schools, particularly vocational high schools in Serang, such as: i) Improving teachers' creativity during this pandemic necessitates the role of principals and stakeholders in improving the school organizational climate with small changes, such as strengthening communication with teachers; ii) Taking into account QWL as one of the elements that impact teachers' creativity by generating a suitable environment; and iii) Taking into consideration QWL as one of the elements that are impactful on teachers' creativity by generating a suitable condition for them when teaching from home, e.g., providing mobile data for online learning so that teachers will not be in the burden of the current situation.

This research has many limitations and shortcomings during its process on account of COVID-19 pandemic, specifically in the data collection process that only utilized questionnaires. Besides, the margin of error used in selecting the sample was 5%, limiting the researcher to take more samples. That was done to prevent the lack of research samples due to this difficult time when face-to-face presence is now tough and worrisome. On that ground, future studies discussing a similar topic are expected to have a smaller margin of error and larger samples and collect the data from observations to gain more accurate information.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was funded by the Ministry of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology through faculty basic research grants. Sincere thanks must be given to the Faculty of Education and Education Management Study Program.

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BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Masduki Ahmad is a lecturer at the Education Management Study Program, Faculty of Education, State University of Jakarta, Indonesia and as Chancellor at As-Syafiiyah Islamic University, Indonesia. His research interests include Education, Education Management, Public Policy, Human Resource Management, Education and Training Management. He can be contacted at email: masduki@unj.ac.id

Suryadi is a lecturer at the Education Management Study Program, Faculty of Education, State University of Jakarta, Indonesia and as the coordinator of the doctoral study program at the State University of Jakarta, Indonesia. His research interests include; Education Management, Educational Management Research Areas, Decision-making, Project management, Leadership and Organizational Behavior, Educational Foundation, Practice Teaching Skills. He can be contacted at email: suryadi@unj.ac.id

Matin is a lecturer at the Education Management Study Program, Faculty of Education, State University of Jakarta, Indonesia and as the coordinator of the Master of Education Management study program at the State University of Jakarta, Indonesia. His research interests include; Education Management. He can be contacted at: matin@unj.ac.id

Sugiarto is a lecturer at the Education Management Study Program, Faculty of Education, State University of Jakarta, Indonesia. His research interests include; Education Management; Leadership, Decision Making, and Public Policy. He can be contacted at email: sugiarto@unj.ac.id